

INTEGRATION OF TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT (TQM) IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTORS THROUGH SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, AND INNOVATION (STI): AN APPROACH TO EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract:

The research aims to identify key elements and factors of integration of total quality management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of leadership characteristics, employee characteristics, and organizational factors. It also measures integration of total quality management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of understanding and commitment of employee respondents, quality effectiveness and improvement of culture, continuous process improvement, focus on requirement of customer, and effectiveness control. Descriptive quantitative research method is utilized in the evaluation of integration of total quality management through science, technology, and innovation approach to effective organization. The study composed eighty (80) participants only. Results indicate that leadership characteristics plays an important role in providing and transforming reality change and vision, show that employee characteristics are more responsible and receptive to various ideas and demonstrate through examples on adequate training, quality, benchmarking, and reward system for employee resistance to change, show that organizational factors provide freedom and mechanism in the hierarchy conduct and rules in constraining flexibility implementation and impediment for TQM-STI. On the other hand, it shows that understanding and commitment of employees ensures the key policies of the TQM through science, technology, and improve innovation of the organizational fundamental process and commitment, shows that quality improvement culture processes and executes to listen the improved quality of total quality management in the organization through science, technology, and innovation, shows that continuous improvement process requires related procedures, policies, and established management control in the organization, shows that customer requirements make partnerships organization happy and close as part of science, technology, and innovation for TQM, and shows that effective control maintains a strict documentation process in evaluating and monitoring the system and process of TQM and STI.

Keywords: Integration of total quality management, and science technology and innovation

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INTRODUCTION

Total Quality Management (TQM) in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation (STI) describes the approach and effort in culture, services, products, and processes in the organization. It focuses on the management system that involves continual improvement practice (Mallillin, & Caranguian, 2023, pp. 131-141). It provides effective communication, data, and strategy to integrate culture and quality discipline of activities. It presents a concept system of modern total quality management. It determines to focus on customer quality and level. It empowers sustainable development goals in TQM through science, technology and innovation (Mayo, & Mallillin, n.d.). It fosters quality improvement in the organization through integrating training, process design, and quality effort on employee involvement, communication process, decision making, continual improvement, systematic approach strategy, integrated system and process centered (Mallillin, et al. 2024, p. 4). It is a standard practice of the management organization as employees to continually analyze the improved process of quality services and products to enhance satisfaction in the TQM performance and services (Magwegwe, 2023). In addition, TQM through STI involves training and implementation of management analytical methods in the operation of the organization. It is a quality planning process and improvement to execute workforce in defining standard operation goals of the organization toward employees' work (Mallillin, 2017, pp. 58-74). It produces competitive advantage in the organizational rapid innovation in science and technology. It contributes to the expansion of worldwide creative output to produce specific hurdles and services. The TQM is capable of demonstrating and adapting science, technology, and innovation to improve and promote decision-making. It empowers the program and awareness of science, technology, and innovation level (Mayo, & Mallillin, 2023, p. 141). It becomes part of TQM through science, technology, and innovation to establish competitive and advantageous organization and sustainability. It aims to help TQM in the organization in acquiring competitive strengths, innovation, technology, strategies, and management transformation (Niyi et al. 2022, p. 8719).

On the other hand, the working process of total quality management implements the proper steps in the assessment of the organization in terms of quality system, assessment, management, core value identity, framework, concept and theory process (Mallillin, 2023, pp. 1-17). It commits management TQM and development quality master plan and priority needs of the consumers. It is based on fundamental implementation, adoption, and principles for careful planning. It involves typically identifying the key values, quality control, mechanism, and culture in the organization integration knowledge system and process (Mallillin, et al. 2020, p. 1). This resolves to embrace the team for total quality management strategy device and integration. It also recognizes the customer requirements and priority. It outlines the team process and caters to customer needs' as necessary. It monitors a special committee towards process and enhancement through innovation of science, technology readiness, and implementation transition (Mallillin, et al. 2020, p. 2). It is the degree of perspective services in the total quality management implementation (Al-Zoubi, et al. 2023, p. 2404). In contrast, the working process of total quality management implementation through science, technology, and innovation involves process and initiative planning and resources of training based on learning theory and global approach in the organizational management (Mallillin, n.d.). It regularizes and sets up systems in the operational management input and consistency of the employees. It refers to the essential elements of the working process for a total quality management system in handling reliability and accuracy. It develops to help the activity of TQM efficient planning effectiveness (Mallillin, 2024, pp. 120-132). It is necessary for the improvement of various ways through the implementation of discovery of science, technology, and innovation. It analyzes and determines the TQM

impact and role in the contribution of planning and continuous improvement process. It contributes to the TQM impact management in supporting modern science, technology, and innovation. It improves employees' lives by the success of TQM method performance (Kadhim, & Mahmoud, 2024, pp. 81-91).

Moreover, the benefits of TQM integration in the system through science, technology, and innovation implement the extremely valuable tool to the fullest. It leads to effective and efficient advantages in the total quality management. It emphasizes the benefits through improved customer satisfaction, understanding expectation and needs in competency of leadership (Caday, & Mallillin, n.d.). It involves feedback in changing the improved system and services of the level of customer satisfaction utilization of TQM organization. It enhances effective operation of the TQM process in a standard manner. This can reduce the errors and reworks for learning resources and utilization process benefits and time. It improves effectiveness of the operation process and innovation through advanced technology ideas and development (Mallillin, et al. 2022, p. 5). It also increases the competitive advantage of TQM focused on various quality competency systems. It is a TQM advantage and competency organization in the system (Alneyadi, 2023, pp. 33-47). In consequence, it builds strong competitive advantage and brand reputation in high quality of service deliverables. It boosts employee morale involvement of total quality management in fostering collaboration, increased productivity, job satisfaction outcome, and performance (Mallillin, 2021, pp. 17-28). It increases innovation to empower quality issues and identifies solutions in solving problems and decision-making. It implements the review of TQM benefits in working to the organization. It discusses the advantages of the TQM standard and focuses on science, technology, and innovation. It describes how to implement the TQM initiated planning process and strategy. It develops and integrates the planning process and system on the strategic importance of TQM through science, technology, and innovation. It prompts the policy in the increased demand of essential control and quality of TQM improvement to be carried in the various approaches and systems. It requires the quality control system to TQM through science, technology, and innovation processes (Geraedts, et al. 2001, pp. 217-220).

Finally, the objective integration of TQM for both public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as the basis for the approach to effective organization develop and explore comprehensive framework and sustainability. It analyzes the current TQM practice assessment and existence within the organization for both private and public sectors on the strengths and weaknesses for improvement. It evaluates the integration of science, technology and improved innovation in utilizing the TQM process. It develops framework holistic design for total quality management principles with science, technology, and innovation in the improved organizational performance and service delivery. It implements to pilot the proposed framework in the selected organization to evaluate potential, effectiveness, and practicability challenges of the process total quality management. It is an approach to science, technology, and innovation for total quality management (Kareska, 2023, pp. 44-57). In contrast, the objectives integration of TQM assess and measure outcome impact of TQM through science, technology, and innovation of organizational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and overall performance metrics to provide recommendation on strategic policy making for organizational leaders and stakeholders on how to effectively sustain and adopt integration of total quality management through science, technology, and innovation framework for long-term benefits. It examines the integration of TQM excellence in the organization to provide a comprehensive overview on the initial process of the TQM system. It proposes the concentrated objectives of TQM through science, technology, and innovation. It manages the total quality system objectives in executing the practical perspective implementation and integration. It indicates

the focal technical integration success and quality driven success in the organization (Komkowski, et al. 2023, pp. 3-15).

Statement of the Problem

1. What are the key elements on the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of
 - 1.1 leadership characteristics,
 - 1.2 employee characteristics, and
 - 1.3 organizational factors?

2. What is the process of TQM integration in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of
 - 2.1 understanding and commitment of respondent employees,
 - 2.2 quality improvement management culture,
 - 2.3 continuous TQM improvement process,
 - 2.4 focus on customer TQM requirements, and
 - 2.5 effectively improved control?

3. Is there a significant correlation between the key elements and factors on the process integration of Total Quality Management (TQM) in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization and the integration of total quality management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization as observed among the participants?

Hypothesis

There is no significant correlation between the key elements and factors on the integration of Total Quality Management (TQM) in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization and the integration of total quality management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization as observed among the participants.

Research Methodology

The descriptive quantitative research design is employed in the concept and process. It features the key elements and factors on the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of leadership characteristics, employee characteristics, and organizational factors. This includes the measure of the integration of total quality management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of understanding and commitment of respondent employees, quality improvement management culture, effectiveness of

improved TQM process, focus on TQM customer and client requirements, and effective improved control process. It is a concept that is utilized in a systematic process objective of quantitative research to analyze and gather numeric information on the data gathered. It examines and provides details of descriptive quantitative research. It is a logical approach and methods in answering the concrete answers specified in the research questions derived from the statement of the problem in the research (Brooke, 2023, p. 84).

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study are the personnel, staff, heads, coordinators, and directors of (DOST), Department of Science and Technology in the different regions in the country. They are the best persons to be utilized because they have experience in the total quality management of the various sectors and organizations in the country through science, technology, and innovation. They continue to innovate the system and process in the implementation of TQM in assisting the organization to the improved operation fullest through advanced technology innovation. This is done through the predefined criteria. The study composed eighty (80) participants only.

Techniques and Sampling Method

Purposive sampling technique is employed in the selection of the sample size from the various personnel at the Department of Science and Technology. It is sometimes called as judgmental, subjective, and selective until the respondents are met according to the predefined criteria. It correlates to the pattern of the study on integration of total quality management as the basis for effective organization. It offsets findings of purposive sampling concerns and information which is non-probability. It seeks to draw a relative sample number sufficient to represent the reasonable warrant and inferences of the entire population. It validates the reliability of the sampling techniques used in the process of the study (Topp, et al. 2004, pp. 33-40).

RESULTS

- 1. On the key elements and factors integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of leadership characteristics, employee characteristics, and organizational factors among the respondents**

Table 1

Elements and Factors of TQM Through STI in Terms of Leadership Characteristics

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. Leadership characteristics ensure pivotal quality services in the organization setting and objectives for total quality management through science, technology, and innovation focused on standard output activities.	3.36	MA	6
2. It plays an important role in leadership characteristics for providing and transforming reality change and vision for science, technology, and innovation for total quality management.	4.24	SA	1.5
3. It focuses on TQM-STI types of leadership characteristics such as transformational and transactional in complying directives in the organization's improved process of the system.	4.00	A	3

4. It enhances TQM-STI in harnessing notable motivation for employee development and accountability in the characteristics of leadership in the organization.	3.88	A	5
5. It emphasizes a strong approach to leadership characteristics implementation of total quality management through science, technology, and innovation.	4.24	SA	1.5
6. It establishes setting directives in the policy initiative of TQM-STI commitment and change effort for the resources and implementation in the organization.	3.92	A	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.940	A	
Standard Deviation	0.323		

Table 1 indicates that rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are "It plays an important role in leadership characteristics for providing and transforming reality change and vision for science, technology, and innovation for total quality management", and "It emphasizes strong approach to leadership characteristics in the process of TQM through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 4.24 or Strongly Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of leadership characteristics is highly observed. Rank 2 is "It focuses on TQM-STI types of leadership characteristics such as transformational and transactional in complying directives in the organization's improved process system", with a weighted mean of 4.00 or Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of leadership characteristics is observed. Rank 3 is "It establishes setting directives in the policy initiative of TQM-STI commitment and change effort for the resources and implementation", with a weighted mean of 3.92 or Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of leadership characteristics is observed. The least in rank is "It ensures pivotal quality services in the organization setting and objectives for total quality management through science, technology, and innovation focused on standard output", with a weighted mean of 3.36 or Moderately Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of leadership characteristics is limited. The overall average weighted mean of 3.940 (SD=0.323) or Agree on the key elements and factors on the process of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in terms of leadership characteristics among the participants.

Table 2

Elements and Factors of TQM Through STI in Terms of Employee Characteristics

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It influences implementation of the improved TQM for STI expectation and logical support to gain greater control on employee work and satisfaction.	3.39	MA	5.5
2. It educates employees to be more responsible and receptive to various ideas of science, technology, and innovation on total quality management characteristics.	4.20	SA	1
3. It provides plausible employee characteristics in the implementation of challenges in the organization for science, technology and innovation total quality management.	4.00	A	3
4. It helps in the improvement of the total quality system through advanced technology and innovation of science in the organization.	3.91	A	4
5. It analyzes the most total quality management action for science, technology, and innovation to be reflected in the organization standard and performance.	3.39	MA	5.5
6. It demonstrates through examples on the link of TQM through STI adequately for training, quality, benchmarking, and reward system for employee resistance to change.	4.09	A	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.830	A	
Standard Deviation	0.354		

Table 2 indicates that rank 1 is "It educates employees to be more responsible and receptive to various ideas of science, technology, and innovation on total quality management characteristics.", with a weighted mean of 4.20 or Strongly Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of employee characteristics is highly observed. Rank 2 is "It demonstrates through examples on the linked of TQM through STI adequately for training, quality, benchmarking, and reward system for employee resistance to change", with a weighted mean of 4.09 or Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of employee characteristics is observed. Rank 3 is "It expands plausible employee characteristics implementation challenges in an organization for science, technology and innovation total quality management", with a weighted mean of 4.00 or Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of employee characteristics is observed. The least in rank is shared by the two indicators which are "It influences implementation of TQM through STI expectation and logical support to gain greater control on the employee work and satisfaction", and "It analyzes the most total quality management action for science, technology, and innovation to be reflected standard process", with a weighted mean of 3.39 or Moderately Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of employee characteristics is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.830 (SD=0.354) or Agree on the key elements and factors of integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of employee characteristics among the participants.

Table 3

Elements and Factors of TQM Through STI in Terms of Organizational Factors

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It is related to total quality management improvement through science, technology, and innovation of ethics and culture in the organization.	3.37	MA	6
2. It provides champions in the organization quality and culture improvement to flourish in the transformation of TQM-STI.	4.00	A	2.5
3. It determines the organizational factors and performance to support the idea of TQM through STI process and manner.	3.97	A	4
4. It strives to work continuously in the organizational factors for TQM-STI to allocate the responsibilities and tasks to be achieved.	3.87	A	5
5. It decentralizes the organizational culture structure flexibility for TQM-STI for the improved process from good, better, and best.	4.00	A	2.5
6. It provides freedom and mechanism in the hierarchy organization conduct and rules in constraining flexibility implementation and impediment for TQM-STI.	4.22	SA	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.905	A	
Standard Deviation	0.285		

Table 3 indicates that rank 1 is "It provides freedom and mechanism in the hierarchy organization conduct and rules in constraining flexibility implementation and impediment for TQM-STI", with a weighted mean of 4.22 or Strongly Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of organizational factors is highly observed. Rank 2 is shared by the two indicators which are "It provides champion in an organization quality culture improvement to flourish in the transformation of TQM-STI", and "It decentralizes the organizational culture structure flexibility for TQM-STI for the improved process from good, better, and best", with a weighted mean of 4.00 or Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of organizational factors is observed. Rank 3 is "It determines the organizational factors and

performance to support the idea of TQM through STI manner”, with a weighted mean of 3.97 or Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of organizational factors is observed. The least in rank is “It is related to total quality management improvement through science, technology, and innovation of ethics and culture”, with a weighted mean of 3.37 or Moderately Agree which means that TQM through STI in the area of organizational factors is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.905 (SD=0.285) or Agree on the key elements factors integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of organizational factors among the respondents.

2. **On the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of understanding and improved commitment of respondent employees, quality process improvement management culture, continuous TQM improvement system process, focus on TQM customer or client process requirements, and effective system control among the participants**

Table 4

Integration of TQM Through STI in Terms of Understanding and Commitment of Employees

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It ensures the key policies of total quality management through science, technology, and innovation of the organizational fundamental process and commitment.	4.21	SA	1.5
2. It recognizes the implication and goals of understanding the commitment of employee success in the organization.	3.36	MA	5.5
3. Employees need to explore and expand what is expected in the organization and why through science, technology, and innovation for total quality management.	4.21	SA	1.5
4. It is a driven commitment and understanding of the employees TQM in the system and organization.	4.00	A	4
5. It shares and understands the process of commitment among employees potential in the mission and vision of the organization.	3.36	MA	5.5
6. It is a commitment for the policies of total quality management success through science, technology, and innovation.	4.12	A	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.877	A	
Standard Deviation	0.407		

Table 4 indicates that rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are “It ensures key policies of the TQM through science, technology, and improved innovation in an organizational fundamental process and commitment”, and “Employees need to explore and expand what is expected in the organization and why through science, technology, and innovation for total quality management”, with a weighted mean of 4.21 or Strongly Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of understanding and commitment of employees is highly observed. Rank 2 is a commitment policy of total quality management success through science technology innovation, with a weighted mean of 4.12 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of understanding and commitment of employees is observed. Rank 3 is a driven commitment and understanding of the employees’ total quality management to the fullest, with a weighted mean of 4.00 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of

understanding and commitment of employees is observed. The least in rank is also shared by the two indicators which are "It recognizes implication goals of understanding commitment to employee success in the organization", and "It shares and understands the process of commitment among employees' potential", with a weighted mean of 3.36 or Moderately Agree which means that integration of TQM through STI in the area of understanding and commitment of employees is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.877 (SD=0.407) or Agree on integration to total quality improved management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of understanding and commitment of employees among the respondents.

Table 5

Integration of TQM Through STI in Terms of Quality Improvement Culture

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It needs to modernize the organizational culture in the improved quality of work based on the employee feedback and concerns.	3.35	MA	6
2. It embraces the improvement of the quality of culture in the organization's knowledge and values in adopting science, technology and innovation of TQM.	4.00	A	3.5
3. It processes and executes to listen on improved TQM in the organization through science, technology, and innovation.	4.23	SA	1
4. The quality improvement culture of the organizational total quality management adopts the process and new ideas for the operation system.	4.00	A	3.5
5. It provides culture quality improvement transparency, values collaboration, and staff empowerment in exhibiting engagement in the organization.	3.83	A	5
6. It increases strong quality and numerous benefits in the organization to improve service quality, customer satisfaction, and efficiency in the operation of an advantaged competency process.	4.07	A	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.913	A	
Standard Deviation	0.304		

Table 5 indicates that rank 1 is "It processes to execute and to listen the improved quality of TQM through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 4.23 or Strongly Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of quality improvement culture is highly observed. Rank 2 is "It provides strong quality numerous benefits in the organization to improve service quality, customer satisfaction, and efficiency in the operation of an advantaged competency process", with a weighted mean of 4.07 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of quality improvement culture is observed. Rank 3 is shared by the two indicators which are "It embraces improvement quality culture in an organization knowledge and values in adopting science, technology and innovation of TQM", and "The quality improvement culture of the organizational total quality management adopts the process and new ideas for the operation system", with a weighted mean of 4.00 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of quality improvement culture is observed. The least in rank is "It provides culture quality improvement transparency, values collaboration, and staff empowerment in exhibiting engagement in the organization", with a weighted mean of 3.35 or Moderately Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of quality improvement culture is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.913 (SD=0.304) or Agree on integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of quality improvement culture among the participants.

Table 6

Integration of TQM Through STI in Terms of Continuous Improvement Process

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It continues to process total quality management through science, technology, and innovation in moving forwards for the delivery output of the organization.	3.76	A	5
2. It requires improvement on the related procedures, policies, and established management control in the organization.	4.20	SA	1.5
3. It makes an effort for total quality management routine in the process and operation of the organizational aspects through science, technology, and innovation.	3.38	MA	6
4. It provides constant improvement and proficiency effort scope of TQM through science, technology, and innovation in the organization.	4.20	SA	1.5
5. It is the continuous process improvement change based on the incremental observation of TQM through STI.	3.98	A	3
6. It is an ongoing improvement of the continuous process of the organization breakthrough, change, and working smoothly.	3.87	A	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.898	A	
Standard Deviation	0.308		

Table 6 indicates that rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are "It requires improvement on the related procedures, policies, and established management control in the organization", and "It provides constant improvement and proficiency effort scope of TQM through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 4.20 or Strongly Agree which means that integration of TQM through STI in terms of continuous improvement process is highly observed. Rank 2 is "It is continuous process improvement change based on the incremental observation of TQM through STI", with a weighted mean of 3.98 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in terms of continuous improvement process is observed. Rank 3 is "It is an ongoing improvement of continuous process of the organization breakthrough, change, and working smoothly", with a weighted mean of 3.87 or Agree which means that integration of TQM through STI in terms of continuous improvement process is observed. The least in rank is "It makes an effort for total quality management routine in the process and operation of the organizational aspects through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 3.38 or Moderately Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of continuous improvement process is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.898 (SD=0.308) or Agree on the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in terms of continuous improvement process among the participants.

Table 7

Integration of TQM Through STI in the Area of Focus on Customer Requirements

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It focuses on customer expectation requirements for the services of the organization and total quality management through science, technology, and innovation processes.	3.37	MA	6
2. It focuses on significant customer requirements in terms of process, essential survival, and building an order of customer relationships.	3.91	A	4
3. It is based on emotion in the business process focused on customer satisfaction and requirements which leads to TQM through STI.	4.03	A	2.5
4. It helps to maintain better efficiency among competitors to expand customer requirements in the organization system and process.	3.79	A	5
5. Focus on customer requirements to make the partnerships in the organization happy and close as part of science, technology, and innovation for TQM.	4.21	SA	1
6. It ensures the price of customers' focus requirements to be understood and to be documented as part of the system in TQM through science, technology, and innovation.	4.03	A	2.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.890	A	
Standard Deviation	0.290		

Table 7 indicates that rank 1 is "Focus on customer requirements to make the partnerships in the organization happy and close as part of science, technology, and innovation for TQM", with a weighted mean of 4.21 or Strongly Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of focus on customer requirements is highly observed. Rank 2 is shared by the two indicators which are "It is based-emotion on business process focus on customer satisfaction and requirements which leads to TQM through STI", and "It ensures the price of customers' focus requirements to be understood and to be documented as part of the system in TQM through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 4.03 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of focus on customer requirements is observed. Rank 3 is "It focuses on significant customer requirements in terms of process, essential survival, and build an order of customer relationships", with a weighted mean of 3.91 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in terms of focus on customer requirements is observed. The least in rank is "It focuses on customer expectation and requirements for the services of the organization and total quality management through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 3.37 or Moderately Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of focus on customer requirements is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.890 (SD=0.290) or Agree on the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of focus on customer requirements among the respondents.

Table 8

Integration of TQM Through STI in Terms of Effective Control

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It measures and monitors the organizational performance and effective control through the TQM and STI process.	3.38	MA	5.5
2. It conforms with the procedures and effective control in TQM and STI maintenance planning, controlling, leading, and organizing.	3.84	A	4
3. It maintains a strict documentation process in evaluating and monitoring the system and process of TQM and STI.	4.21	SA	1.5
4. It focuses and quantifies the improvement and objectives of effective control in the organizational TQM through STI.	4.00	A	3
5. It provides effective control of the finances in the organization especially on the expenditures against the profit for quality management to the fullest.	4.21	SA	1.5
6. It describes the power of effective control in the organization to identify and verify the total quality management system through science, technology, and innovation.	3.38	MA	5.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.837	A	
Standard Deviation	0.380		

Table 8 indicates that rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are "It maintains a strict documentation process in evaluating and monitoring the system and process of TQM and STI", and "It provides effective control of the finances in the organization especially on the expenditures against the profit for quality management to the fullest", with a weighted mean of 4.21 or Strongly Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of effective control is highly observed. Rank 2 is "It focuses or quantifies the improvement objectives of effective control in the organizational TQM through STI", with a weighted mean of 4.00 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of effective control is observed. Rank 3 is "It conforms with the procedures and effective control in TQM and STI maintenance planning, controlling, leading, and organizing", with a weighted mean of 3.84 or Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in terms of effective control is observed. The least in rank is also shared by the two indicators which are "It necessary measures or monitors organizational performance and effective control through TQM and STI process", and "It describes the power of effective control in the organization to identify and verify the total quality management system through science, technology, and innovation", with a weighted mean of 3.38 or Moderately Agree which means integration of TQM through STI in the area of effective control is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.837 (SD=0.380) or Agree on the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of effective control among the participants.

3. On the significant correlation between the key element factors, integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization.

Table 9

Test of Significant Correlation Between the Key Element Factors and the Integration of TQM through STI

Test of Variables	Computed r value	Interpretation	Decision
Leadership Characteristics:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understanding and improved commitment of respondent employees 	0.028787	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quality TQM improvement culture 	0.028654	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continuous TQM improvement in process 	0.028709	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> focus on customer or clients requirements 	0.028738	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> effective TQM control process 	0.028936	not significant	acceptance of Ho
Employee Characteristics:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understanding and improved commitment of respondent employees 	0.029197	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quality TQM improvement culture 	0.029062	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continuous TQM improvement in process 	0.029118	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> focus on customer or clients requirements 	0.029148	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> effective TQM control process 	0.029349	not significant	acceptance of Ho
Organizational Factors:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understanding and improved commitment of respondent employees 	0.028915	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quality TQM improvement culture 	0.028782	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continuous TQM improvement in process 	0.028837	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> focus on customer or clients requirements 	0.028867	not significant	acceptance of Ho
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> effective TQM control process 	0.029066	not significant	acceptance of Ho
One-tailed test, df of 80 at 0.05 level of significant, with critical r value of 0.217185			

Table 9 indicates that when the variables are tested against each other, it reveals that all computed r values are lower than the critical r value of 0.217185 which is not significant and non-rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, it is safe to say that there is no significant correlation between the key elements and factors integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization and the integration of total quality management in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization as observed by the participants.

DISCUSSION

It reveals that the key elements and factors of integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of leadership characteristics among the respondents plays an important role in providing and transforming reality change and vision in the organization. It emphasizes a strong approach to leadership characteristics implementation of TQM through science technology innovation. It contributes to implementing leadership characteristics to the principles of TQM. It sheds light to the performance and leadership roles in the improvement of the TQM in the organization. It fosters excellence innovation and development (Ahmed, & Sajid, 2023, pp. 37-55). On the other hand, leadership characteristics focus

on TQM-STI types for transformational and transactional in complying directives in the organization's improved process of the system. It establishes setting directives in the policy initiative of TQM-STI commitment and change effort for the resources and implementation. It ensures pivotal quality services in the organization setting and objectives for total quality management through science, technology, and innovation focused on standard output activities. It provides improved quality of science, technology, and innovation transformation for total quality management aspects. It explores characteristics leadership influences that connotes quality system and process such as innovation, learning, improvement, process, and performance (Glogovac, et al. 2023, pp. 313-329).

In comparison, the key elements and factors of integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of employee characteristics among the respondents educates employees to be more responsible and receptive to various ideas. It demonstrates through examples on the link of TQM through STI adequately for training, quality, benchmarking, and reward system for employee resistance to change. It ascertains employee performance, job satisfaction and job features. It assesses the work satisfaction of employee involvement and influence in the organization. It demonstrates engagement of employee performance in a dynamic organization in the present era (Hidayat, 2023, pp. 1652-1659). In addition, the employee characteristics provide plausible implementation of challenges in the organization for science, technology and innovation total quality management. It influences implementation of TQM through STI expectation and logical support to gain greater control on employee work and satisfaction. It analyzes the most total quality management action for science, technology, and innovation to be reflected in the organization standard and performance. It is determined to motivate individual employee work and support. It enhances the optimistic effect for employee characteristics in the target objectives and resources. It is necessary in the existing total quality management through science, technology, and innovation contribution and achievement services (Sukma, et al. 2023, pp. 51-57).

Furthermore, the key elements and factors integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of organizational factors among the respondents provide freedom and mechanism in the hierarchy conduct and rules in constraining flexibility implementation and impediment for TQM-STI. It provides champions in the organization quality and culture improvement to flourish in the transformation of TQM-STI. It decentralizes the organizational culture structure flexibility for the TQM-STI improved process of the system. It formulates a framework for total quality management in organizational performance through science, technology, and innovation. It provides an orientation contingency approach for TQM content effectiveness and efficiency (Ahinful, et al. 2024). In addition, organizational factors determine the performance to support the idea of TQM through STI process and manner. It is related to total quality management improvement through science, technology, and innovation of ethics and culture. It focuses on the TQM innovation of employees and mediating role in the organization. It provides innovation and practices in organizational behavior through science, technology, and innovation. It contributes to the knowledge of TQM in elucidating the employees' role in enhancing innovation to offer insights for better organization. It adopts an effective dimension to improve better outcomes to achieve customer satisfaction. It provides proper strategic management in the organizational factors competency and effectiveness (Arhin, & Cobblah, 2024, pp. 26-41).

Moreover, the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science technology innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of understanding and commitment of employees among the respondents

ensures organizational fundamental process. Employees need to explore and expand what is expected in the organization and why through science technology innovation for TQM. It is a commitment policy for total quality management success through science, technology, and innovation. It examines and explores the organizational commitment and understanding of employee performance. It influences employee increase and growth to positive change from good, better, and best (Rifa'i, 2023, pp. 41-48). In consequence, it is a driven commitment and understanding of the employees' total quality management to the fullest. It recognizes goals of understanding commitment of talents' success in the government organization which will be applied to private sectors. It shares and understands commitment among employees' mission and vision. It is a result of a positive effect in understanding commitment of employees especially on efforts and performance. Commitment and understanding among employee performance mediates in the working ability. It develops and improves the increased performance of employees. Commitment and understanding of employees is an asset to the organization (Prayogi, & Annisa, 2023, pp. 112-122).

Apparently, the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science technology innovation as an approach to effective organization in terms of quality improvement culture processes and executes to listen in the organization. It increases strong quality and numerous benefits to improve service quality, customer satisfaction, and efficiency in the operation of an advantaged competency process. It develops framework concept performance for TQM and continuous process and improvement. It explores to transform and to explain the quality improvement culture through TQM and contribution of advanced technology and innovation. It discusses the importance of TQM in the improvement of culture for a better success and failure system and process (Ugwu, 2023, pp. 352-369). Hence, it embraces the improvement quality of culture knowledge and values in adopting science, technology and innovation of TQM. The quality improvement culture of total quality management adopts the process and new ideas for the operation system. It provides culture quality improvement transparency, values collaboration, and staff empowerment in exhibiting engagement. It determines the impact and purpose of success and implementation of TQM and organizational culture and values among the system and process. It implements the success of science, technology, and innovation through total quality management respectively. It focuses on the effect of customers' process management and leadership. It also focuses on the performance result of quality improvement culture as part of social responsibility in the community and employees (Mohammad, 2006, pp. 606-625).

Certainly, the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of continuous improvement process among the respondents requires improvement on related procedures, policies, and established management control. It provides constant improvement and proficiency effort on the scope of TQM through science technology innovation. It continuously processes improvement change based incremental observation of TQM through STI. It develops a fundamental goal and concept framework in the continuous improvement for TQM. It explores variables in the continuous improvement process and connection through TQM science, technology, and innovation (Enyinna, 2024, pp. 1-12). Also, it is an ongoing improvement of the continuous process of the organization breakthrough, change, and working smoothly. It makes an effort for TQM routine operation of the organizational aspects through science, technology, and innovation. It is the process in the TQM practice performance of employees' nature and consensus. It influences the continuous improvement process practice and strategy in the organizational total quality management. It mediates the TQM performance and practices continuous improvement strategy. It provides better effect in ensuring continuous

improvement process strategy in craving the organization competitive advantage to the fullest (Jimoh, et al. 2019, pp. 162-177).

Notably, the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science technology innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of focus on customer requirements among the respondents makes the partnerships in the organization happy. It is based on emotion in the business process focused on customer satisfaction and requirements which leads to TQM through STI. It ensures the price of customers' focus requirements to be understood and to be documented as part of the system in TQM through science, technology, and innovation. It conceptualizes to integrate the supply chain and sustainable organization model for customer satisfaction through science, technology, and innovation orientation and quality value perception. It mediates the effect of focus on customer requirements based systems of TQM through science, technology, and innovation (Asha, et al. 2023). In addition, it focuses on significant customer requirements in terms of process, essential survival, and builds an order of customer relationships. It also focuses on customer expectation and requirements for the services of the organization and total quality management through science, technology, and innovation processes. It recognizes the competitive landscape in the quality services of the organization to the customers' value and retention. It plays a significant strategic operation in achieving goals which focus on customer requirements. It aligns with the customer focus objectives, operational strategies, and to enhance service quality. It fosters an increased strong customer relationship retention process (Al Kurdi, et al. 2023, pp. 27-38).

Finally, the integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of effective control among the respondents maintains a strict documentation process in evaluating and monitoring. It balances effective control finances in an organization especially on the expenditures against the profit for quality management to the fullest. It focuses and quantifies the improvement and objectives of effective control in the organizational TQM through STI. It delves into the control practice and compliance of TQM. It measures effective control of organizational impact and mechanism compliance to obtain total quality management through science, technology, and innovation (Biseko, 2023). Lastly, it conforms with the procedures and effective control in TQM and STI maintenance planning, controlling, leading, and organizing. It is necessary to measure and to monitor the organizational performance and effective control through the TQM and STI process. It describes the power of effective control in the organization to identify and verify the total quality management system through science, technology, and innovation. It defines the continuous intention of the organization. It treats the challenges and effective control in an organization. It addresses the intention of effective control for the success and failure of the company. It maintains the impact of the TQM expectation control system and process in the organization. It preserves and accumulates knowledge of effective control to the management intention of the organization (Frezatti, et al. 2023, pp. 1145-1176).

CONCLUSIONS

It shows that key elements and factors integration of TQM in public and private sectors through science, technology, and innovation as an approach to effective organization in the area of leadership characteristics among the respondents plays an important role in providing and transforming reality change and vision where it emphasizes strong approach to leadership characteristics implementation of TQM through science technology innovation and

focuses on TQM-STI types of leadership characteristics such as transformational and transactional in complying directives in the organization improved process system.

It shows that key elements to TQM through STI in the area of employee characteristics among the respondents educates employees to be more responsible and receptive to various ideas and demonstrates through examples on adequate training, quality, benchmarking, and reward system for employee resistance to change and provides plausible employee characteristics in the implementation of challenges in the organization for science, technology and innovation total quality management.

It shows that organizational factors among the respondents provides freedom and mechanism in the hierarchy conduct and rules in constraining flexibility implementation and impediment for TQM-STI where it provides champion in the organization quality and culture improvement to flourish in the transformation of TQM-STI and decentralizes the organizational culture structure flexibility for TQM-STI for the improved process.

It shows that commitment and understanding of employees among the respondents ensures the key policies of TQM through science technology innovation and fundamental process and commitment where employees need to explore and expand what is expected in the organization and why through science, technology, and innovation for TQM and commitment policies of total quality management success through science, technology, and innovation.

It shows that quality improvement culture among the respondents processes and executes to listen the improved total quality management in the organization through science, technology, and innovation where it increases strong quality and numerous benefits in the organization to improve service quality, customer satisfaction, and efficiency in the operation of an advantaged competency process and embraces the improvement quality of culture in the organization knowledge and values in adopting science, technology and innovation of TQM.

It shows that continuous improvement process among the respondents requires related procedures, policies, and established management control in the organization where it provides constant improvement and proficiency effort scope of TQM through science, technology, and innovation. It is change based on the incremental observation of TQM through STI.

It shows that customer requirements among the respondents make the partnerships in the organization happy and close as part of science, technology, and innovation for TQM where it is based on emotion in the business process focus on customer satisfaction and requirements which leads to TQM through STI and ensures the prize of customers' focus requirements to be understood and to be documented as part of the system in TQM through science, technology, and innovation.

It shows that effective control among the respondents maintains a strict documentation process in evaluating and monitoring the system and process of TQM and STI where it provides effective control of the finances in the organization especially on the expenditures against the profit for quality management to the fullest and focuses and quantifies the improvement and objectives of effective control in the organizational TQM through STI.

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